

The trigger factors of domestic violence among mothers during pregnancy

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ABSTRACT

Domestic violence also called "domestic abuse" or "intimate partner violence", can be defined as a pattern of behavior in any relationship that is used to gain or maintain power and control over an intimate partner. Abuse is physical, sexual, emotional, economic, or psychological actions or threats of actions that influence another person. This includes any behaviors that frighten, intimidate, terrorize, manipulate, hurt, humiliate, blame, injure, or wound someone. Furthermore, it is common among women, which globally increases the risk of pregnancy. This research aimed to analyze the trigger factors of domestic violence among pregnant women. The interviews with eight participants were analyzed using the Colaizzi method. It produced five main themes, namely, the husband is often angry and fight since having an affair, income is not sufficient to fulfill the monthly needs, fights because the husband feels jealous, the husband is temperament, smacks, and also berates when drunk, fights because husband spends money on gambling.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Violence is a way of solving problems, such as a way of feeling offended or disappointed about unfulfilled desires. Men often assume that harsh treatment should be imposed on women, thinking that this method will make women independent and obedient. This action shows that men use their physical strengths more often to solve problems in relationships [1]. Women are most at risk and often suffer from violence, especially during pregnancy [2]. The sustainable development goals (SDGs) have re-focused on gender equality and are committed to combating all forms of violence against women and girls. In this case, domestic violence is most common for women, which globally increases the risk of pregnancy [3].

Violence may likely start during or before pregnancy, the experience of violence before pregnancy can increase, decrease, or remain the same [4]. International reports on the number of violence against women during pregnancy vary widely from 5% to 69.9% [5]. In a study comparing women who experienced violence with women who had never experienced violence, it was found that women who had experienced violence had more frequent social and family problems, substance abuse, menstrual and reproductive disorders, as well as problems with sexually transmitted infections (STI), musculoskeletal and gastrointestinal (GI) disorders, chest pain, abdominal pain, headaches, and can also experience urinary tract infections (UTI) [6].

Mothers who have been victims of violence during pregnancy pose a serious threat not only to themselves but also to the fetus and affect the development of children. The mother and the fetus in the womb can suffer from side effects, such as maternal death, mental health disorders, fetal death, maternal weight loss during pregnancy, premature delivery, inappropriate size of the baby for gestational age, low birth weight, kidney

infections, and also increased the possibility of undergoing surgery at delivery [7]. The violence that occurs is also closely related to high levels of depression during pregnancy (at 18 weeks of gestation) and at eight weeks postpartum. In addition, it also affects behavioral problems for 42-month-old children [8].

The causing factors of domestic violence during pregnancy are pregnancy itself which triggers jealousy and control of the perpetrator, violence before pregnancy, young women, unwanted pregnancies, and reproductive control [9]. Based on customs and culture, pregnancy is usually seen as a pleasant event in a woman's life where a child is expected to bring a new generation into the family [10]. Pregnancy is also thought to change a woman's life, introducing her to new experiences. On the other hand, pregnancy is often a time of joy and hope characterized by maternal optimism, emotional upheaval and the need for more support [11]. In addition to bringing happiness, pregnancy can also increase the risk of partner violence for millions of women of reproductive age worldwide [12]. Violence may begin during pregnancy or may have started before pregnancy. If you have experienced violence before becoming pregnant then this may increase, decrease, or remain the same throughout pregnancy [13]. International reports on the number of violence against women during pregnancy vary widely from 5% to 69.9% [14].

According to National Commission on Violence Against Women the incidence of violence against women for the province of NTT in 2019 was reported 104 cases [15], and in 2020 there were 758 cases [16], there was a fairly high increase in one year. Many factors can cause domestic violence cases to continue to increase in the West Manggarai Regency. According to Nafi [17] the reinterpretation of traditional values that began to shift can also be one of the causes of violence against women, one example is the reinterpretation carried out by community members towards 'belis', where many cases later occurred in the community. as a result of the implementation of this purchase. West Manggarai is one of the areas in East Nusa Tenggara that still holds patriarchal culture that makes men feel they have full power over their wives. This is what makes researchers interested in conducting research related to domestic violence against mothers during pregnancy in West Manggarai Regency. Hence, the research aimed to study the trigger factors of domestic violence among pregnant women in West Manggarai Regency, East Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted in West Manggarai Regency, East Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia. It employed qualitative design using a phenomenological descriptive approach. The subjects were eight mothers who had experienced domestic violence during pregnancy, who were selected using a targeted sampling technique until the data were saturated. Determination of the number of research subjects (respondents) is considered adequate if it has reached the level of redundancy (saturation). In this study, the criteria for participants include: i) mothers who in the last two years during pregnancy have experienced domestic violence; ii) volunteer willing to be a research participant; iii) able to tell the experience of experiencing domestic violence; iv) domiciled in West Manggarai Regency.

The process of recruiting participants was carried out through tracing cases of domestic violence that occurred in West Manggarai Regency and in collaboration with the Office of Population Control, Family Planning, Women's Empowerment and Child Protection (DP2KBP3A), West Manggarai Police and the Labuan Bajo Women's and Children's Protection House which very active in paying attention to cases of domestic violence in West Manggarai Regency and also through the sub-district to traditional leaders in several villages. After the researcher got the mother's data, the researcher contacted and asked for permission. For mothers who agreed to act as participants, the researcher gave an explanation sheet about the study. Mothers who agreed to participate were asked to sign a consent form and an in-depth interview was conducted.

Informed consent was obtained from the respondents before starting the interview, which contains the sensitive nature of the interview questions. However, they were allowed to withdraw from the research at any stage of the interview. The interview was conducted in a quiet place to ensure the privacy of the respondents and maintain the confidentiality of the information. Adequate time was given beforehand to build trust and report back to respondents. The interview was conducted using a guideline containing series of open-ended questions about experiences of domestic violence during pregnancy.

The data were collected through in-depth interviews and direct observation by making field notes interviews with participants for approximately 60 minutes. The type of interview used is a semi-structured interview so that researchers will use interview guidelines but are not fixated on interview guidelines, researchers provide opportunities for participants to convey experiences and meanings found by participants in experiencing domestic violence. In this study, the approach used by the researcher is descriptive phenomenology which consists of four stages, namely bracketing, intuiting, analyzing and describing [18]. The interview questions were prepared by the researcher and validated by two supervisors. The interview questions described the lived body, lived time, lived space, and lived human relations to understand the world of life

experiences. Interviews were conducted at the village head's house and the traditional leader's house according to the participant's request.

Furthermore, the thematic analysis used consisted of several stages using the Colaizzi method [19] by involving two or more people who are experienced in analyzing and interpreting qualitative data to reduce the possibility of biased interpretations from researchers, namely involving supervisors in providing input and checking the arrangement of verbatim transcripts to interpreting research data and setting themes. The recording of the interviews was listened to again and transcribed word for word, then the keywords of the categories were identified, which were then grouped into sub-themes. The results were then grouped into one theme.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of eight respondents were interviewed. They are in the age range of 22 to 36 years old, West Manggarai people, and Catholic. Characteristic of respondents is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents

Respondents	Respondents' age	Husbands' age	Respondents' education	Husbands' education	Respondents' occupation	Husbands' occupation	Marriage age
1	29	34	Elementary school	Bachelor	Teacher	Teacher	Two years
2	28	32	Elementary school	Elementary	Farmer	Farmer	Six years
3	28	29	Elementary school	School	Midwife	Teacher	Two years
4	22	25	Diploma III	Bachelor	Housewife	Driver	One year
5	26	33	Junior high school	Elementary	Farmer	Farmer	Seven years
6	36	33	Junior high school	School	Teacher	Entrepreneur	Eight years
7	26	27	Elementary school	Junior high school	Housewife	Shop employee	Five years
8	22	28	Elementary school	School	Housewife	Private employee	Five years
			Bachelor	School			
			Senior high school	Senior high school			Five years
			Senior high school	School			
			Senior high school	Bachelor			

In this research, five themes were reported as the determining factors of domestic violence against pregnant women. They are: i) the husband is often angry and fights because he's having an affair; ii) the income is insufficient to fulfill the monthly needs; iii) the husband oftentimes fights because he feels jealous; iv) the husband has the temperament, smacks, and also berates when drunk; and v) the husband fight because he spends money on gambling. Table 2 summarizes the relevant sub-themes and themes.

Table 2. Themes and sub-themes for causing factors of domestic violence

Themes	Sub-Themes
Husband is often angry and fights since having an affair	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Husband is often angry for no reason and fought since having an affair • Husband gets angry in talking about his affair • Fighting because husband rarely comes home • Becoming angry in checking the husband's cellphone
Income is not sufficient to fulfill the monthly needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient money for monthly needs and forced to work • Husband gets angry if sending money to family
Fights because husband feels jealous	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Husband is jealous when using a cellphone • Fighting because of jealousy if wife talking to other men
The husband is temperament, smacks, and also berates when drunk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The husband becomes temperamental, kicks and hits when drunk • The husband curses when drunk • Husband gambles even though having no money
Fights because husband spends money on gambling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being angry because money runs out for gambling • The money from the sale is used for gambling • Beaten for asking for money that ran out

3.1. The husband is often angry and fight because he is having an affair

The respondent felt that the husband's behavior began to change because he is having an affair leading to a fight. The husband also often gets angry for no apparent reason:

... We started arguing ever since I caught him cheating on me. (P3)

...since he cheated on us, we've been fighting all the time, there's always a problem.... (P5)

...we often fight because I caught him cheating on me, since then, we have never experienced peace.... (P6)
...he is often temperament and lies ever since he became close to that girl, as well as small problems often becomes a big issue.... (P5)
...I think he always suddenly got angry without any specified reason ever since he started getting close to that girl.... (P3)

The husband is not happy if the respondent wants to discuss his relationship with other women, he will feel uncomfortable in talking about his cheating and end up fighting:

...He got angry when I asked him if he still has a relationship with the mistress because I'm afraid they're still in a relationship.... (P1)
...If I start a conversation about the mistress, he will end up fighting with me. It's like he doesn't like when I talk about that woman.... (P6)

Since he started having an affair, the husband rarely comes home and often stays out without telling the reason. This leads to a fight between the couples:

...he rarely returns to Lembor (the village where he lives), although he used to be diligent. Since he cheated on me, he comes home infrequently...and that's what makes us fight when he comes home (P6)
...sometimes he also doesn't come home and I don't know where he sleeps. When I ask him, he gives many reasons and unclear answers... (P5)

Since the husband started having an affair, the cellphone can no longer be held by the respondent because he will get angry and end up fighting:

...he was angry with me because I insisted to look at his cellphone because he forbade me. I know there was a message from his mistress, although I used to be free to check his cellphone (P3)
...he always hides his cellphone, if I insist to take it, we will fight... (P5)

Contextually, this theme means that the husband becomes angry and often quarrels since his husband deviates. Since having a relationship with another woman, the husband has become more temperamental, so he often gets angry and ends up fighting. This theme is based on participants' statements stating that they have often quarreled since their husband cheated on them, husbands are often angry for no reason since they cheated on them, husbands are emotional when asked about their infidelity and fight because their husbands rarely come home, husbands are angry when they open their husband's cellphones.

This is in accordance with the results of Agboola's [20] where infidelity is one of the factors a person commits acts of domestic violence where the marital relationship begins to be disturbed since the husband has an affair. Having an affair causes domestic violence such as a social, economic, emotional, and psychological attack, as well as sexual and physical violence [21]. In marriage, it can be associated with physical violence related to normative gender roles. Men who have sexual partners at the same time are more likely to experience physical violence, for example, because of a bond with a male identity that emphasizes sexual submission and male dominance [22]. Women who believe that their husbands have illegitimate sexual partners outside can react violently out of jealousy and anger [23]. Furthermore, men may use violence in response to accusations of the affair by their partners [24].

3.2. The income is not sufficient to fulfill the monthly needs

The husband is angry when the money is used up before the end of the month, and feels that the respondent is wasteful, although she feels that she has been very frugal.

...we argued because I asked for money to buy baby needs just before giving birth. He said I was wasteful because the money ran out quickly, although I had saved a lot... (P4)
...he always advised me not to be extravagant without knowing household needs.... (P6)
...he said I was too extravagant, that's why I always lack money, although I think I've saved a lot (P8)

...My husband gets angry quickly when I ask for money for shopping when he stops working, we find it difficult to meet our needs. Nevertheless, I ask for money because we need to eat.... (P7)

When I asked him for money for household needs, I've never done that without nagging, so I'm lazy to ask.... (P6)

...maybe because he's the only one looking for money, and therefore he gets angry every time the money runs out before the end of the month. Therefore, no matter what, I have to make use of the money well to avoid fighting... (P8)

...That was the first time he hit me because he forced me to go to work in the fields while I was five months pregnant. He said to quickly pay the handyman at that time we were building a house... (P2)

The husband will often get angry if the respondent sends money to help her family because it is not sufficient to meet the monthly needs:

... I was once beaten for sending money to my younger brother to pay for college, even though it was my salary. My husband said that my brother was not our responsibility anymore because we don't have enough money to meet our monthly needs... (P6)

...It's a really difficult condition, we have to send money to help our parents but my husband will not understand. We always fight when he finds out that I send money to my family in the village, he says we have to be rich first before helping people... (P3)

Contextually, this theme means that income or income (money and so on) does not meet the needs of life every month. Insufficient monthly money causes quarrels between participants and husbands. This theme is based on participants' statements stating that they are accused of being extravagant because spending money runs out quickly, angry when participants ask for money, forced to work to increase income, husbands are angry if participants send money to their families.

This is in line with the research by Samangun and Rapamy [25] which found that one of the causes of domestic violence is economic factors where work can trigger domestic violence, if the work turns out to be low-income or even because of odd jobs so that the income cannot meet the family's living expenses. The need that swells even though the income is large can trigger domestic violence. The results of Nafisah's research [26] also found that the most dominant factor influencing the occurrence of domestic violence was financial (economic) factors. Financial (economic) problems are often the cause of violence in the family, where financial (economic) conditions cannot meet the needs in the family. This is also in line with the research by Setiawan [27] where the most common factor behind the occurrence of domestic violence is economic problems.

One of the causing factors of violence in society is economic. The economic pressure causes the delinquents in the greatest need to urge violent acts. The perpetrator vents by committing violence against people in the household environment [28]. There is a tendency that financial difficulties in a family lead to violence. However, from an economic perspective, rich families are possibly selfish [29]. This problem arises from the many demands for daily needs while the income generated is not sufficient. Therefore, it makes both husband and wife parties at odds end in domestic violence [30].

3.3. Fights because husband feels jealous

The husband forbade the respondent to use cellphones (HP) to contact other men. This is based on excerpts from interviews with respondents:

....He's angry because I'm using a cellphone and forbid me, he's afraid that I'm texting another man... (P4)

...he slammed my cellphone because he was jealous of people having comments on Facebook (FB), and then prohibit me from using cellphones... (P8)

The husband is suspicious and doesn't like seeing respondent talking to other men even though it's just a co-worker and a house neighbor:

...he was jealous when I had a conversation while laughing with someone in our village too, that's why he hit me.... (P2)

....When he picked me up, I still had conversations with my male friends in front of the workplace, which lead to fighting at home the moment when we arrived....(P6)

.... We've been fighting a few times because he's jealous because I talk to other men.... (P3)

Contextually this theme has the meaning of fighting or bickering because the husband feels less trusting or suspicious. This theme is based on participants' statements stating that their husbands are jealous if they use their cellphones and fight and get hit because they talk to other men.

From an evolutionary point of view this kind of jealousy can be seen as an expression of mate care [31]. Jealousy is a method used by the perpetrator to control the victim. The problem of jealousy is a direct trigger for violence and results in injury to the victim and a trigger for ongoing relationship stress [32].

Research shows that women are more prone to violence because of jealousy or suspected relationships, especially during pregnancy [33]. This has also been shown in research, where jealousy and suspicion of having an affair were associated with the risk of domestic violence [34]. In an interview, one woman reported that she had experienced physical and sexual violence, was more jealous and possessive, as well as allegations of relationships between her and her husband during pregnancy [35]. A survey on 284 male perpetrators in US domestic violence treatment programs found that men also reported increased severity of violence during their partner's pregnancy, as well as increased jealousy and possessive behavior such as checking on their partner's whereabouts, limiting activities outside the home, and limiting partner contact with family and friends [36]. Furthermore, jealousy and possessiveness imply that a person responds excessively to indications of his partner's attraction to the opposite sex and tries everything possible to prevent intimate contact [37].

3.4. The husband is temperament, smacks, and also berates when drunk

The consumption of alcoholic beverages anesthetizes the husband's consciousness and become out of control, and therefore becomes irritable when someone disturbs him and ends up hitting:

...I often avoid him when he's drunk. It's because he's violent with me when I ask him when he's drunk... (P7)

.... I grumbled because he drank a lot, he jumped and kicked me in the back. When he's drunk, he doesn't even care about the pregnant wife.... (P8)

...If he's drunk, I don't dare go near him because he gets temperament.... (P2)

...We always fight when he's drunk because he becomes very temperamental,and he slapped me.... (P3)

When the husband is drunk, he often experiences emotional changes, he is more easily angered, also often speaks harshly and insults the respondent:

...even though I speak pleasantly when he's drunk, he still curses me... (P5)

...My husband often act violently and speak harshly, sometimes he will keep cursing me until the neighbors hear him... (P8)

...I don't like it when he's drunk and says rudely,... (P4)

Contextually, this theme has the meaning of getting hit and reproached and getting vile words (speech) when the husband is drunk (because of drinking too much alcohol. This theme is based on the participant's statement that the husband plays hands) when drunk, kicking when drunk, quick-tempered when drunk, slapping, also cursing and insulting when drunk.

In a small qualitative study of victims of violence during pregnancy, many respondents reported being assaulted when their partner was drunk and violence increased when their partner was drunk [38]. Individual and societal beliefs that alcohol causes aggression can drive behavior. Experiencing violence in a relationship can lead to alcohol as a reason for violent behavior [39]. When both partners have been drinking, the role of alcohol may be greater because of the potential of alcohol to influence thinking, perception and risk taking of both partners. That is, both partners are more likely to misunderstand the other's behavior, less able to resolve situations without assault, and more likely to engage in risky assault. Social and cultural perceptions of alcohol may also play a role where acceptance and tolerance of alcohol-related bad behavior (including assault), can influence drinkers' expectations about their drinking behavior. This means that, regardless of the effects of alcohol, some people who have been drinking may intentionally assault or abuse their partners because they have the expectation that their behavior will be excused on the basis that they have been drinking at the time [40].

This research shows that the woman is exposed to violence because her husband is drunk. It agrees with Wilson *et al.* that there is a clear association between alcohol consumption and domestic violence [40]. The results are also in line with Hove *et al.* which showed the role of alcohol in partner violence [41]. Women whose partners have alcohol problems are three times more likely to experience violence during pregnancy [42]. The consumption of alcohol directly affects cognitive and physical function, reduces self-control, and

makes individuals less able to negotiate without violence. Excessive drinking exacerbates financial difficulties, parenting problems, affairs, or other family pressure. This can lead to tension and conflict in a marriage, increasing the risk of domestic violence [43].

3.5. Fights because husband spends money on gambling

Fights usually occur when the respondent is angry because the husband is spending money on gambling. Besides, the husband also uses the money from the respondent's sales to gamble. He will be angry if he is questioned, thereby leading to a fight:

..I have no money but he gambles again. If I am angry because the money ran out, he replies with the same attitude, therefore we fight..... (P2)

...he complained that he had no money but instead he gambled. This must have made me angry, but he replied with the same attitude... (P4)

...I asked for the money he used for gambling, he said I insulted him. That's the money from the sale, but I was hit in the stomach..... (P5)

...one time, he brought one million to gamble but came home without bringing money at all, then I became angry and we fought... (P3)

Contextually this theme has the meaning of bickering because the husband uses up the money to gamble. Quarrels usually start from participants who are angry because their husbands spend money on the gambling table, not only that the husband also uses the money from the participants' sales to gamble, when asked the husband will scold the participants again so that it ends in a fight. This theme is based on participant statements stating that husbands gamble even though there is no money, fight because money is used up for gambling, selling money is used for gambling, beaten for asking for money that is used up, emotional because money is used for gambling. Hing research [44] found that gambling causes partner violence, this study also highlights the prevalence of economic abuse in women who experience gambling-related domestic violence.

In this research, violence also occurs as a result of the husband's hobby of gambling. According to Jackson *et al.* most of the 32 respondents who were interviewed in-depth, reported that gambling generally causes domestic violence as a reaction to anger and deep-rooted distrust, while victimization is a result of gambler anger due to direct gambling losses and frustrations [45]. Financial abuse is also a form of domestic violence, when the gamblers get too deep with addiction, they will not stop merely monopolizing all the money for themselves in the process of depriving the family and even physically harming if they get in the way. Therefore, gamblers are more prone to violence due to financial inadequacy, and other pressure such as spouses or children who do not support them in gambling addiction, and stigma from other societies [46]. Gambling causes problems in the home environment characterized by strife and deprivation, loss of household or personal money, arguments, anger and rudeness, lies and deception, neglect of family, negatively affected relationships, poor communication, confusion, and development of gambling problems, and others [47].

4. CONCLUSION

The interviews with eight participants were analyzed using the Colaizzi method and resulted in five main themes, namely, the husband is often angry and fights because he is having an affair, the income is not sufficient to fulfill the monthly needs, the husband fight often because he feels jealous, the husband is temperament, smacks, and also berates when drunk, the husband fight because he spends money on gambling. These factors trigger domestic violence against pregnant women.

A domestic violence education program is needed. It is important to find out the right reception and screening for victims through an understanding of their feelings, appropriate communication skills, and effective interventions. Future research should include women from different backgrounds, identification of high-risk groups, the relationship between partner personality and violence, and men's perceptions of their violent behavior.

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